

How will the Greek innovation ecosystem evolve by 2035?

Environmental Scanning & Trend Analysis

Assignment submitted by

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Assignment #1

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| INTERNATIONAL CERTIFIED FUTURE STRATEGIST |

Contents

1	Executive Summary.....	3
2	Introduction	4
3	Methodology: Identifying external factors	5
4	Trends & Uncertainties	6
4.1	Affordable XaaS: Continuous drop in ICT infrastructure costs...	6
4.2	Digitisation Acceleration continuous	6
4.3	Increase of online banking	6
4.4	Sharing economy booms	7
4.5	Online Learning Adoption	7
4.6	Uncertainties	7
5	Causal Analysis.....	8
6	Conclusion.....	9
7	Appendix:.....	10
7.1	Trends Analysis of Driving Forces and Consequences.....	10
7.2	Uncertainties Analysis of Driving Forces and Consequences ...	10
7.3	Consequence Trees	11
8	References	12

COURSE	INTERNATIONAL CERTIFIED FUTURE STRATEGIST 2021
ASSIGNMENT	HOME ASSIGNMENT #1
SUBJECT	FOCAL QUESTION AND FIRST ENVIRONMENT SCANNING
GOAL	Use the course’s knowledge in a specific contextual environment analysis.
TASK	Identify a client, purpose and focal question. Do a contextual environment analysis for this purpose and focal question where you use the methods that have been examined during the first module.
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1 Executive Summary

This report was submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements of the [International Future Strategist Certification Programme](#) by KAIROS. It is the first of three assignments and aims to replicate an actual case study. The case presented herein is an actual case and although it does not involve at this stage a wide participation of stakeholders, hopefully it creates a good starting point for further research.

The subject is **innovation** and the question around which the research evolves is “**How will the Greek innovation ecosystem evolve by 2035?**”. What can we expect from it? What are the key factors, both trends and uncertainties that impact it, how are they interrelated and how important are they?

This **report covers** the first stage of the foresight study: the environmental scanning and trends analysis. Given the time and resources restriction, this is done using simple tools of analysis: desk research, online libraries, open data and simple visualisations. Only a limited engagement of few stakeholders was possible at this stage mainly through feedback in already identified factors. A virtual [collaborative space serves](#) as a showcase of the findings and an easy way for providing comments and insights.

The **report contains** an introduction with a brief description of the context, the focal question and the client. Ten trends and 10 uncertainties are presented along with a more detailed description for the 5 more important trends. The interconnections between these trends are analysed using a Cross Impact Analysis and are reported in a table form and a causal loop diagram. Finally, a trend analysis of the driving forces and consequences of 5 trends and 4 uncertainties along with a visual presentation of 2 consequence trees is also included in the appendix.

Innovation is a fascinating subject and more importantly it runs across sectors, themes and industries. Although the report targets the Greek ecosystem, most of the factors that impact innovation are not country or even continent specific. My goal is to identify how the process of innovation may evolve and what could and should the stakeholders do to further promote and support it as a driver for growth and prosperity.

	<p><i>Do you want to contribute?</i></p> <p>If you would like to access the collaborative space used in this report and give feedback you can access it without the need for login here: http://bit.ly/InnoGreece You can use the comment feature to provide any kind of feedback, thought or insight.</p>
	<p><i>Feedback & Comments in this report</i></p> <p>You can comment on this document by following this link: http://bit.ly/ICFS_1_OS</p>

2 Introduction

The importance of **innovation** in the growth and prosperity of our society and world at large is not a matter of argument or dispute. Intuitively, we all consider innovation a positive value, a critical factor for success, and entrepreneurs, businesses and governments are all striving to reach as a high level as possible. As our societies evolved and became more interconnected, further interdependent, richer in information and more complex in structure, the idea of innovation evolved with them.

To understand innovation, we need to take a step back and examine not specific sectors or products but the **process** of it and how the whole value chain of innovation operates and morphs into an **ecosystem**. The state of these innovation ecosystems is vital for growth and progress. They can be local, regional, national or even cover larger geographical areas like Europe, including both EU member states but also neighboring countries, participating in the EU R&D initiatives.

*In this context I decided to study the **Greek Innovation Ecosystem**, which is of course highly interconnected with the EU one, and examine **how it may evolve in the next 15 years, till 2035**.*

I examine not innovation in a specific industry or sector but rather, the **process of innovation**. How Greece and EU have sponsored and will promote innovation and support new ideas that can lead to economic development and growth. This **timeframe** was selected because it expands beyond current framework programmes and initiatives (Horizon Europe, Next Generation Europe, Greece 2.0) and will help us be better prepared for the next generation of funding and initiatives.

Greece went through a harsh financial and political crisis which started in 2009, as an aftermath of the global financial crisis of 2008, and culminated in 2015 with a referendum that came very close from costing even the country's own place in EU. Today, the country is in a much better state and despite the disruption and destruction caused by COVID19, stroke some important wins. It has the luxury of thinking more **strategically for the future**. It has a new **strategic plan** aligned with EU priorities and the means to implement it through EU Next Generation Recovery Fund, increased Foreign Direct Investment and cheaper access to capital.

The primary purpose of the study is to help the client, **International Development Ireland Ltd. (IDI)** identify opportunities in Greece and in the area, find new services in innovation support that will be needed by the private and public sector and even examine the possibility of establishing a new innovation hub or a regional office in the area.

What is innovation?

It is **not just** technology:

Innovation is the use of new ideas, products or methods where they have not been used before. (Eurostat, 2012)

Innovation is the multi-stage process where organizations transform ideas into new/improved products, service or processes, in order to advance, compete and differentiate themselves successfully in their marketplace. (Baregheh et al., 2009)

See also:

(OECD Oslo Manual, 2018)

What is an innovation ecosystem?

A loosely interconnected network of companies and other entities that coevolve capabilities around a shared set of technologies, knowledge, or skills, and work cooperatively and competitively to develop new products and services.

(Moore, 1993)

International Development Ireland (IDI)

A provider of innovation support, capacity building and technical assistance to public and private organisations. [www.idi.ie]

3 Methodology: Identifying external factors

An environmental scan and trend analysis is by definition a collaborative exercise that requires high stakeholder engagement. Given the time and resources restrictions, in this study I focused mainly on existing desk research and short interviews with 10 colleagues, partners and clients involved in the Greek and European innovation space.

The desk research and interviews mostly corroborated my own understanding, formed throughout my 20 years involvement in innovation and technology. However, the opportunity to discuss with various professionals coming from different organisations and sectors offered a better understanding on the **perceptions of innovation** and the **different points of view within each stakeholder group**.

I started the environmental scanning using the tools that were introduced

in the course and facilitating an online collaboration space ([Mural](#)). I first identified factors using the EPISTLE+M framework and assigned them in the 3 world circles. I moved on the historical view of the factors trying to identify the major events in the contextual environment that impacted innovation and moved on to the near and inner world. Since my target year is 2035, I started my timeframe 20 years before today (2000), however in the near world I added some older but

significant events that changed the course of innovation. Undoubtedly, most of the events, especially in the outer world are technological breakthroughs, political landmarks and financial earthquakes that shocked the world and redefined priorities. In the near world I tried to follow the evolution of the R&D support in EU and in Greece with the various initiatives, agencies and policies.

Throughout this desk exercise, I kept asking the same questions and searching in the literature and news for answers:

- What were the biggest events/breakthroughs/shifts in technology, politics, economy, science, environment & society?*
- How have they affected EU, Greece, government and business sector?*
- What are the mega trends and trends that appear now in research and in the major news?*

Mural Collaboration

I created a [Mural canvas](#) where I collected all information. Its use offered an easy way of presenting ideas and findings and involving other people in the process. I decided to keep the process tightly monitored and I shared my collaboration space locked requesting only comments once work in each section was presentable. [\[LINK\]](#)

4 Trends & Uncertainties

A trend & uncertainties scanning exercise for the innovation space in Greece cannot ignore the global trends and developments or the major European initiatives and policies that directly impact the Greek landscape. It is clear therefore that the **identified trends are not unique to Greece**. All of them however have a specific Greek aspect which is identified.

<p>Cheap/Affordable XaaS</p> <p>Technology becomes more and more affordable, with faster, cheaper and more accessible, scalable and secure cloud tools. Distributed models (blockchain), AI, IoT networks, 5G, broadband. Companies benefit from affordable purchase of services (XaaS).</p> <p>Why is Important? Startups/Spinoffs/ Entrepreneurs have access to cheaper, secure, fully scalable infrastructure.</p> <p>Greek Aspect Greece follows the trend although some services like mobile internet and 5G still cost more than the EU average.</p>	<p>Digitisation Acceleration</p> <p>EU (and others) see digitisation of all industries as a prerequisite for progress, development and growth. Digital solutions are needed to disrupt old, established, traditional technologies (food processing & Production). COVID19 accelerated this trend.</p> <p>Why is Important? It is enhancing connectivity, financial inclusion, access to trade and public services. It can help a society transform into a more equal.</p> <p>Greek Aspect Greece is doing major steps to Digitisation and now (2021) has a Digital Transformation Bible 2020-25.</p>	<p>Climate Change Awareness</p> <p>Despite deniers, governments and International Organisation acknowledge the problem and take initiatives and actions to fight global warming, extreme weather, sea rise, loss of Biodiversity, Resource Scarcity. Initiatives have major impact in companies strategies.</p> <p>Why is Important? Without urgent and decisive action, the world will change turning large parts of the earth into uninhabitable wastelands.</p> <p>Greek Aspect Country will be affected from climate change with extreme weather, higher temperatures, arid years, decline in agriculture production.</p>	<p>Aging Population (Demography)</p> <p>Population aging strains social insurance and pension systems and challenges existing models of social support. It affects economic growth, trade, migration, disease patterns and prevalence, and fundamental assumptions about growing older.</p> <p>Why is Important? Without urgent and decisive action, the world will change turning large parts of the earth into uninhabitable wastelands.</p> <p>Greek Aspect A major problem in Greece threatening sustainability of public insurance and pensioning system.</p>	<p>Online banking use increase</p> <p>Online payment, contactless cards, mobile payments, new online banks make it easier for new companies to accept payments and create business banking accounts. Corporate banking becomes more affordable and offers more options.</p> <p>Why is Important? New financial innovations may help startups access capital and funds easier and more affordable.</p> <p>Greek Aspect Country was lacking behind in financial innovations. However, post financial crisis adoption of credit cards and online payments increased significantly. See VIVA</p>
<p>Skills Shortages</p> <p>Certain skills, especially STEM but also soft skills are lacking from the industry and young generations are not eager to pursue more demanding education and training. Skills gap is a critical barrier for growth and competition for the best people helps only bigger players.</p> <p>Why is Important? Both industry and research cannot fulfil their needs for skilled and agile personnel. Without cultivation, talent is wasted.</p> <p>Greek Aspect Greece lost more than 500.000 skilled professionals due to financial crisis. Education curriculum is outdated.</p>	<p>Online Learning wide adoption</p> <p>Accelerated by the COVID19 pandemic online learning became almost a commodity. Improvements in AR and VR are added to the portfolio. Students from all grades all over the world turned to online learning and became familiar with the process, new tools and online presence and collaboration.</p> <p>Why is Important? Education and Lifelong Learning are driving forces for a better life and future through personal development.</p> <p>Greek Aspect Greek higher education institutions suffer from unskillfulness and disruptions in their operations caused by small groups or radicals. Private Universities are banned by constitution.</p>	<p>Sharing Economy booms</p> <p>Evolution of sharing economy through collaboration of individuals, peer-to-peer networks, etc. creates new models of businesses, new activities and markets. Crowdfunding provides a new source of funding for startups.</p> <p>Why is Important? Startups/ entrepreneurs can benefit by tapping into the power of large distributed networks for access to money, skills, resources.</p> <p>Greek Aspect Greece followed the trend amid a lot of resistance from established groups (e.g. Taxi drivers against Uber)</p>	<p>Health/Safety Importance</p> <p>The disruption of COVID19 pandemic made the already present trend for better health and wellbeing even more prominent. Implications in work environment, welfare, care services. Rapid progress in life sciences (CRISPR, RNA) will transform medicine.</p> <p>Why is Important? Without healthy society there is no healthy economy. Breakthroughs in life sciences will also drive other sectors.</p> <p>Greek Aspect Hospitals are understaffed and National Health System overwhelmed. COVID19 crisis forced gov to improve and invest more in the sector.</p>	<p>Decline of Trust</p> <p>Declining trust levels in science, governments, international organisations, experts, media due to populist movements, propaganda from authoritarian states, dissemination of mis/disinformation. Examples: Conspiracy theories, anti-vaccination, deniers.</p> <p>Why is Important? Lack of trust erodes the fabric of society, leads to polarisation and societal anger.</p> <p>Greek Aspect The populist movement hit Greece especially after 2010. Rise of fascist political parties and radical left.</p>

Out of the above trends the most prominent and predictable are the following.

4.1 Affordable XaaS: Continuous drop in ICT infrastructure costs

With technology becoming more and more affordable a trend where almost everything will be offered as a Service (XaaS) is eminent. We see this today with cloud computing, streaming services for music and movies and online subscriptions for any kind of service you can imagine from news to gym classes. In fact, this trend coupled with the sharing economy creates new distribution models even for traditional products. Think about extending leasing beyond cars and upgrade programs beyond phones.

4.2 Digitisation Acceleration continuous

If **Affordable XaaS** is about infrastructure and hardware, **Digitisation** is about SW. The COVID19 pandemic accelerated digitisation in many sectors and introduced new habits with “touchless” transactions. From retail, to health, to delivery, to government. This clear trend needs to be further expanded in scope and in sectors. The trend is backed by all EU and national policies and supported by significant budget.

4.3 Increase of online banking

Every business needs a safe and secure banking environment in order to receive payments from clients and fulfill financial transactions with suppliers, partners and personnel. Innovative businesses need a **secure financial environment** that will simplify the processes and allow them to

XaaS & Cloud Computing

XaaS is a general, collective term that refers to the delivery of anything as a service. (Bigelow, 2017)

The continuous drop of costs in both computing power and telecom will expand opportunities for innovation. (Kim, 2017; *Trends in the Cost of Computing*, 2020)

The case of AWS is an excellent example. (Long, 2021)

operate with higher efficiency. The wide adoption of online payments and the increased use of credit cards and contactless payments due to the pandemic restrictions, helped accelerate this already present trend. In addition, new fully online banks and financial institutions are gaining ground and adding thousands of new customers monthly. As a result, banking becomes more affordable and both companies and consumers have plenty of more options.

4.4 Sharing economy booms

Internet and mobile computing offered enormous power to every single person, created networks and communities and allowed direct communications between private individuals often with no need for intermediaries. The sharing economy evolved through this notion and made available frictionless collaboration between individuals. New peer-to-peer networks appeared, sparking new business and financing models, from crowdfunding to peer-to-peer lending, to carsharing, to house renting. Startups and entrepreneurs can benefit from this trend by tapping into the power of large, distributed, decentralized networks for access to money, skills, resources.

4.5 Online Learning Adoption

Accelerated by the COVID19 pandemic online learning became almost a commodity. Improvements in AR and VR are added to the portfolio. Students from all grades all over the world turned to online learning and became familiar with the process, new tools and online presence and collaboration. Although it became quite clear that physical contact and face to face learning cannot be replaced, it eliminated distances and barriers.

4.6 Uncertainties

In the case of trends, we know pretty well, or at least we can predict with a safe degree of confidence their direction. However, there are factors that it is impossible to predict how they will evolve or which direction they will move. These are our uncertainties.

Online banking

The role of banking in innovation is vital not only because they can and should provide funding, but because every new product or service involves transactions. And only a safe, trusted, secure, affordable and innovative banking environment can guarantee them.

(Fasnacht, 2020; Lin et al., 2018)

Sharing Economy & innovation

According to a recent paper *“With the emergence of the sharing economy paradigm, the process of innovation is no longer unidirectional, but cyclical.”* (Abhari et al., 2019)

Sharing economy disrupts traditional business models and introduces new products and services. It allows innovators and entrepreneurs to think in a new more inclusive and collaborative way. (Emprechtinger, 2018)

<p>Geopolitical Environment</p> <p>Political situation in EU, SE Europe, Turkey, Middle East and of course Greece can have a major impact in the Greek Innovation ecosystem. Examples: a hybrid war with Turkey, a war in Middle East which forces Greece to take sides, a new refugee wave.</p>	<p>Globalism vs. Nationalism</p> <p>Pandemic spread and disruption of value chains challenged the globalisation trend. EU is moving towards "Strategic Autonomy" consolidating its resources and trying to minimise dependence from third countries.</p>	<p>Role of Government</p> <p>The role of government is crucial since a lot of R&D is subsidised and involvement of government in innovation can be a major driver. In contrast a populist government will create more barriers and will inhibit meritocracy.</p>	<p>Financial Environment</p> <p>A stable financial environment will promote growth and support funding risky innovations. In contrast a new financial crisis either as an aftermath of the pandemic or due to structural problems still looming in EU will diminish the available funds for innovation.</p>	<p>Workplace changes</p> <p>COVID19 with its social distancing and isolation rules, imposed radical changes to the work environment. WFH became the norm for 2020 and seems that it is a trend that will remain. The future of the office as we know it, is uncertain yet.</p>
<p>Swift Response EU and Greek government respond effectively and swiftly in a coordinated manner and mitigate the problem.</p> <p>Uncoordinated Efforts Response from International Institutions mixed. Divisions in EU. Loss of allies. Indecisive Greek government.</p>	<p>Globalisation 2.0 Globalisation trends prevail although players may change (e.g. production in Vietnam instead of China)</p> <p>Strategic Autonomy Europe manages to consolidate its production and value chains for critical products.</p>	<p>Greece 2.0 Government supports innovation, provides incentives, invites back scientist working abroad. Creates a long term vision.</p> <p>Indifference Government does not value science and research. Defunding. Takes an indifferent, or even negative stance to innovation.</p>	<p>Stagflation Companies and governments cannot overcome the pandemic crisis and are losing ground and value rapidly.</p> <p>Growth Huge amounts of new money revitalise the market (USA Economic Plans, Next Gen Europe) create growth conditions.</p>	<p>Stagflation Companies and governments cannot overcome the pandemic crisis and are losing ground and value rapidly.</p> <p>Growth Huge amounts of new money revitalise the market (USA Economic Plans, Next Gen Europe) create growth conditions.</p>
<p>World Order</p> <p>Emerging economies BRICS (Brazil, Russia, India, China, S. Africa) push for a new world order and brake out from the established International institutions (WTO, UN, IMF, etc). EU (and Greece) is looking for a more strategic role in this new environment.</p>	<p>Current & New Pandemics</p> <p>Although the developed world is progressing rapidly in the fight against COVID-19, the future of the pandemic through mutations or new epidemic crisis before event we fight this one may arise. Developing world is lacking behind in this fight and will have a global impact.</p>	<p>New Ethics & Privacy</p> <p>Breakthroughs in science (CRISPR) and technology (AI) lead to new ethical challenges. It's unclear how society will respond to these challenges, who is going to take hard decisions and how. Societal demand may lead to further regulation and barriers.</p>	<p>Cryptocurrencies evolve</p> <p>The crypto market attracts more and more attention from private businesses and from governments. Financial institutions devise their strategies taking into account these asset classes with yet uncertain future.</p>	<p>Disruption of Education</p> <p>Traditional higher education providers rediscover their role by embracing new learning models, active collaboration with the industry and government. New players in learning disrupt the education space by introducing new tools, models, ideas.</p>
<p>Equilibrium International Organisations are restructured and reformed to address needs of emerging economies.</p> <p>Pushback Older powers respond with protectionism and trade wars. EU is affected, without being able to find a clear path.</p>	<p>Back to Normal Vaccination pace picks up globally, we manage to contain the pandemic and return to normality very similar to past.</p> <p>Years of Pandemics Despite breakthrough in developed world, parts of the developing world face long term health crisis and some collapse.</p>	<p>Ethical Science Governments and companies agree on a balanced approach that minimises ethical risks while allowing scientific use.</p> <p>Ethical Barriers Governments impose barriers to research and restrictions to use in fear of societal backlash. No R&D for ethically disputed.</p>	<p>Store of Value Bitcoin and other major cryptocurrencies become store of value and are widely acceptable.</p> <p>Hyper Regulation Governments impose strict regulatory frameworks, erasing all cryptocurrency advantages and benefits.</p>	<p>Ubiquitous Learning Universities adapt to new learning models, certification of skills by industry, Lifelong learning paths. Private universities in Greece.</p> <p>Death of University Traditional universities become irrelevant. People get training from anywhere and certify it through networks.</p>

5 Causal Analysis

As we work on the environmental scanning, and we identify new trends and uncertainties it becomes clear that a lot of them are interrelated. Societal needs push scientists to address specific problems and their solutions often create new habits, new lifestyles, often new problems. In that sense a **Cross Impact Analysis** is necessary to understand the relations between the factors and identify the most important ones.

I decided to use all 10 identified trends to get a clearer image of their dependencies and importance. Organising them into the table and assigning values to them verified the importance of some while revealed that some identified trends may have a lower relevance than originally thought.

FACTORS Dependand Driving	Affordable XaaS	Digitisation Acceleration	Climate Change Awareness	Aging Population (Demography)	Online banking use increase	Skills Shortages	Online Learning adoption	Sharing Economy booms	Health/Safety importance	Decline of Trust	TOTAL
	Affordable XaaS		3	1	1	3	2	3	3	2	1
Digitisation Acceleration	3		1	0	3	1	3	3	1	1	16
Climate Change Awareness	0	2		1	1	2	2	2	3	2	15
Aging Population (Demography)	0	0	1		1	2	1	1	2	2	10
Online banking use increase	2	2	0	1		1	1	3	1	1	12
Skills Shortages	0	1	0	0	1		3	1	1	1	8
Online Learning adoption	2	3	0	0	3	3		2	1	2	16
Sharing Economy booms	3	3	1	1	2	0	2		1	1	14
Health/Safety importance	0	1	3	3	0	0	0	0		1	8
Decline of Trust	0	1	2	1	2	1	1	2	2		12
TOTAL	10	16	9	8	16	12	16	17	14	12	13

- A - Affordable XaaS
- B - Digitisation Acceleration
- C - Climate Change Awareness
- D - Aging Population (Demography)
- E - Online banking use increase
- F - Skills Shortages
- G - Online Learning adoption
- H - Sharing Economy booms
- I - Health/Safety Importance
- J - Decline of Trust

6 Conclusion

As these lines are written, in June 2021, we still try to understand the real, long term impact of the biggest global pandemic of the last 100 years. So far Greece seems to have survived the harshest part and emerged from the crisis with new optimism. The crisis accelerated some long overdue initiatives and **digitisation** was largely adopted in the governmental sector with a unified government portal currently providing thousands of different government services to citizens, including an electronic prescription service and a mobile platform for the cabinet to function remotely. Moreover, in the private sector the majority of businesses (90%+) recognise the growing importance of digital transformation. (*The Digital Transformation "Bible" of Greece (2020-2025)*, n.d.)

At the same time, we can see serious attempts of restructuring the **higher education sector** with key initiatives addressing problems that plague the Greek Universities for decades (lawfulness, violence, pure quality, outdated courses). (Kalyvas, 2021; Papaioannou, 2021)

The **startup space** is being organised and a new law giving clear tax incentives to Angel Investors and VCs is in place. In addition to the above a government bodies responsible for **R&D and Innovation** are restructured and adopt most of the well-justified and valid suggestions from a recent study by DIANEOSIS think tank (Kalogirou et al., 2021).

All the above initiatives are supported and interrelated to a new strategic plan. The first that the country has produced in many years. "**Greece 2.0**" as it is termed aims not only to help the economy recover from the COVID-19 pandemic but is a chance for the country to make a leap to the future.

Greece will be able to implement the above plans thanks to approximately 30 billion euros from the European Union's 750-billion-euro Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) and expects another 27 billion euros from inexpensive loans and investors over the next six years.

The major trends like drop in ICT infrastructure costs, the digital acceleration, the boom of sharing economy, increase of online banking and learning and a renewed interest on climate change are global. Their course cannot change by whatever happens in Greece. The importance of health and hygiene and a combination of the above will also impact the future of work.

There are, however, some very important uncertainties for Greece like the geopolitical situation in our area, the health of the global and EU financial environment, the role of government. These factors can go either way, positively or negatively for the country and it is very difficult to predict at this point. After a decade of a harsh financial crisis, today, the future looks almost bright. It is our job to do whatever we can to realise it.

Greece 2.0

Greece 2.0 strategic plan is based on the "Development Plan for the Greek Economy" prepared by a commission of experts chaired by Professor Sir Christopher Pissarides, the 2010 Nobel laureate for economics.

(*A New Economic Plan for Greece: What Future?*, 2021)

7 Appendix:

7.1 Trends Analysis of Driving Forces and Consequences

TREND ANALYSIS OF DRIVING FORCES AND CONSEQUENCES			
DRIVING FORCES What makes the trend happen?	TREND	CONSEQUENCES What does the trend lead to?	HYPOTHESES Long term consequences?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Declining costs of computing - Expanding of connectivity - Declining costs in Telecom - Need for constant connectivity 	Affordable XaaS Lowering prices of online services and plethora of available tools.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - More accessible computing for startups allows easier implementation of their ideas. - Close to zero costs for infrastructure. - New business models and services for both B2C, B2B 	Businesses and consumers move to a model where almost everything is offered as a Service (XaaS). Traditional ownership models decline.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Need for further efficiency - Strive for cost reduction - Promise for a better/ faster/ cheaper service/ product. - Inevitable future (Digitise or perish) 	Digitisation Acceleration Transformation of Analog into digital for every aspect of business, life, government.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - New or improved services/ products - Interaction between business < - > governments - Ability for deep analysis (Big Data, AI) - Preservation of Information & Knowledge - Easier Disaster Recovery - Income generation from new ideas, business 	Every business is a digital business. Digitisation facilitates integration of different business verticals through industries blending together and merging. Physical and Digital spaces are blurred. Major consequences in the future of work and life.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Experience of extreme phenomena in everyday life - A new generation more environmentally responsible - Global Activism (Greta) - Compounding scientific proof 	Climate Change Awareness Global warming, extreme weather, biodiversity loss, scarcity of resources are acknowledged as major problems. Actions taken by governments & businesses.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Governments and International organisation taking initiatives and imposing new regulations - Businesses adopt environmentally responsible policies (ESG a requirement) - Citizens and consumers demand policies / actions. - Shift to renewable energy, decarbonisation, nuclear (?) 	Hopefully, immediate dangers are mitigated. Long term strategy by International Organisations (UN) leads to some valid results. However, danger is not easily averted. Some countries are more affected than others. Shift of agriculture production North since South too hot.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Experience of extreme phenomena in everyday life - A new generation more environmentally responsible - Global Activism (Greta) - Compounding scientific proof 	Skills Shortages Lack of necessary technical and soft skills from workforce. Low interest of young generations to pursue these more demanding skills.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Less and less well trained people available for demanding and challenging works. - Lower quality workforce - Scarcity of specific skills, capabilities and experiences. - Ruthless competition for talent between corporations and smaller businesses 	Disruption of traditional education models. New corporate training and continuous learning are adopted. Companies provide initiatives for training into certain skills similar to military (guarantee payments, tax incentives, insurance etc.)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Internet communities/ networks - Mobile economy (apps) - Decentralisation - Resource Efficiency 	Sharing Economy boom Wide adoption of new work models of sharing economy, peer-to-peer networks.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - New decentralised networks and collaboration opportunities - Increased efficiency of resource usage - Changes in the work models 	New models of ownership and work. You do not need to own (almost) anything when you can easily find it through a network.

7.2 Uncertainties Analysis of Driving Forces and Consequences

UNCERTAINTY ANALYSIS OF DRIVING FORCES AND CONSEQUENCES			
DRIVING FORCES What makes the trend happen?	UNCERTAINTY	OUTCOMES	CONSEQUENCES What does each outcome lead to?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A new financial crisis - Unchecked inflation - Cost of climate change - Geopolitical Reasons 	Financial Environment Global, European and Greek economy.	A leap forward: Innovation Europe EU respond swiftly with a common strategy and make a leap forward by investing in innovation. Surviving the next crisis EU steps up but not enough. Innovation is no longer a priority. EU still cannot agree on a common strategy.	EU and Greece see the new crisis as an opportunity for further actions to support innovation & position as a global player. Greece cannot realise its plans without enough EU support. The environment is not good for supporting new ideas and startups amidst a global crisis.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Unresolved Issues - Authoritarian States - Injustice and poverty - New Civil wars - Refugee & Migration - Turkey's attitude 	Geopolitical Environment Situation in SE Europe and M.East.	A frail peace Status quo continuous with no major changes. EU takes a bigger role in the area. New alliances and active EU (France), USA role, deter aggressiveness. Sporadic microcrisis There is no major crisis but sporadic smaller conflicts and standoffs, inhibit growth and cost a lot.	Greece establishes a new diplomacy, based on soft power and strong alliances with major players. Defence sector embraces innovation. Greece navigates and tries to insulate its economy and society from these crisis but the instability of the area holds back major investments from abroad (FDI).
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Unresolved Issues - Authoritarian States - Injustice and poverty - New Civil wars - Refugee & Migration - Turkey's attitude 	Role of Government How Greek administration responds to the challenges of the environment and what long term vision it creates.	A vision for the future Government adopts an ambitious vision for the future and manages to implement it successfully. A vision without actions Vision is there but cannot be realised or it becomes a half baked version mired with more problems than solutions.	Greece establishes a new diplomacy, based on soft power and strong alliances with major players. Defence sector embraces innovation. Government succumbs to populism and does not go through with necessary structural changes. Populist parties disrupt the political space creating a new crisis.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - COVID19 persistence - Demands by employees - Social Insecurity - New work habits - Drive for Digital Nomads - Business Real Estate 	Workplace future Changes in the workplace, WFH.	A destination for Digital Nomads Greece becomes top destination for attracting talent and building new synergies between them and local ecosystem. Digital Nomads potential unutilized Digital Nomads come but no added value created. Only a useful tourism product.	Digital Nomads become the bridge to link local innovation ecosystem with global players. A whole sector and ecosystem is built around this notion. Digital Nomads remain indifferent and uninterested in the Greek Innovation ecosystem. Innovation stakeholders cannot benefit from their presence.

7.3 Consequence Trees

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